

Lumpy Skin Disease – A Havock for Livestock Animals

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Introduction

Lumpy skin Disease also known as (LSD) is an emerging disease and has created a deadliest impact on the cattle's and buffalos. This disease is being transmitted by the virus of genus Capripox belonging to family poxviridae. The Virus is also known as "Neethling Virus". It was first reported in Zambia way back in 1929, recently in Bangladesh in 2019 And now in India. The virus is spreading its roots in different states of India including Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Punjab, Uttar Pradesh, and Rajasthan. Within the short time span virus achieved to have plenty number of deaths to create havoc in India. Out of which large number of about 75000 deaths were recorded in Rajasthan state only. In order to control the deaths and spread of virus Govt. of India has stopped the interstate transport of animals along with livestock melas and bullock cart races.

How animals get infected?

The disease is transmitted by the biting flies and mosquitoes and small insects from one animal to another as it is an arthropod born disease. Also, introduction or mixing of diseased animals with healthy animals has been the major contributing factor in spread. Also, it is transmitted through the contamination of food and water and water.

Clinical Signs and Symptoms Shown by the Animals

Being an infectious disease fever is the first symptom shown by the animal, temperature of animals rises up to 105-106 °F and may persist for a week. Another, symptoms include the anorexia, emaciation, nasal discharge, swollen lymph nodes, respiratory distress, conjunctivitis, poor growth, edema of limbs, brisket region and limbs which makes animal lame etc. The characteristic symptom shown by the animals is appearance of the large number of nodules, which

are round, circumscribed, firm, painful and slightly raised all over the body whose size may ranges from 3-6 cm, (Fig.1) which causes rejection or poor value of hide and thus making the economic loss to farmers. The milk yield of animal also gets decreased which causes further losses to dairy industry. In some animal's abortions was also been reported.

Fig.1 Nodules on the body of animals

Fig.2 Burning of neem leaves for repelling flies and mosquitoes

Fig.3 Goat pox vaccine used for LSD Vaccination

Myths and Facts:

- 1) Milk from infected animal should not be consumed: No, you can consume it without any worry just need to boil it before consumption.
- 2) It gets transferred from infected animals to humans: No, it doesn't get transferred from infected animals to the humans by any means as it is not a "zoonotic" disease.

Conclusion:

As this disease is caused by the Virus there is no permanent cure to this disease but still animal can be saved by doing the proper veterinary aid like medications including analgesics,

fluids, antibiotics to control secondary bacterial infections, applying fly repellent on wounds so that maggots should not grow in the wounds, doing vaccination, quarantine or isolation of diseased animals, providing the clean, disinfected water, good quality of feed. The goat pox vaccine is being used for vaccinating the animals (Fig.3). Also taking care of flies and mosquitoes by burning the neem leaves along with the dung (Fig.2), cleaning of the animal sheds at regular intervals. Farmers should wear gloves and mask while milking the animals so as to avoid contamination. Farmers as well as consumers need not to believe on the rumors that milk from the infected animal should not be consumed, you can consume it without any worry just need to Pasteurize it before consumption. Most importantly this disease is not the zoonotic disease. In case of death of animal, carcass should be disposed properly and the premises should be disinfected properly.